

UWS CoARA Action Plan (2026-2030)

Introduction

There is now a strong and widely shared consensus across the research community that reforming research assessment is essential to support sustainable research quality and healthier research cultures. This is reflected in a growing body of influential international initiatives, including the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment ([DORA, 2013](#)), the Leiden Manifesto ([2015](#)), the *Metric Tide* report ([2015](#); revisited in [2022](#)), and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA, [2022](#)). Alongside these developments, the higher education sector has seen increasing attention to open research, research integrity, and issues such as equality, diversity, bullying, and harassment. Collectively, this work has underscored the critical role that assessment systems play in shaping the environments and behaviours through which research is conducted ([Curry, Gadd & Wilsdon, 2022](#)).

Responsible research assessment seeks to address these challenges by ensuring that evaluation practices “incentivise, reflect and reward the plural characteristics of high-quality research, in support of diverse and inclusive research cultures” ([Curry et al., 2020, p. 4](#)). By adopting such approaches, research organisations can better align assessment with their institutional values and strategic priorities, remain responsive to evolving expectations of good research practice, and support work that addresses pressing societal, environmental, democratic, and economic challenges.

By joining CoARA in 2025, University of the West of Scotland (UWS) committed to embedding these principles in its approach to research assessment. This includes developing criteria and processes that prioritise quality, impact, diversity, inclusivity, and collaboration, while ensuring that ethical standards, integrity, and rigorous scientific practice are never undermined by inappropriate incentives. These shared commitments for research assessment reform, to be achieved in an agreed timeframe, will enable recognition of the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality of research and its resulting impacts, facilitate a move away from inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics, and reinforce trust in research.

As a CoARA member, we committed to producing and sharing this action plan within one year of signing the agreement, and to reviewing it within five years of signing the agreement, with at least one cycle of review and evaluation completed within that time. This action plan therefore covers the period August 2026 – August 2030. Annual progress reports will be shared with the Research Innovation Committee, and key activities and milestones will be showcased externally as appropriate. At the conclusion of this action plan, a progress report will be shared externally and a renewed action plan will be produced.

At UWS, these commitments are not being adopted in isolation. They directly support the delivery of the University’s Strategy 2030 ambitions for research and innovation, including our focus on impactful, inclusive, and globally relevant research aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. They also build on our established participation in sector-recognised frameworks that promote positive research culture and researcher development, including the HR Excellence in Research (HREiR) award, the Technician Commitment, and our alignment with the principles of the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). This action plan therefore brings together these strands into a coherent approach to responsible research assessment, ensuring that how we evaluate research actively reinforces the behaviours, values, and outcomes that UWS seeks to promote.

Our Commitments

UWS's commitment to responsible research assessment is aligned with complementary institutional and sector frameworks, including:

- **HR Excellence in Research (HREiR):** Supporting fair, transparent, and inclusive approaches to researcher recruitment, development, and progression.
- **Technician Commitment:** Recognising the vital contributions of technical staff within the research ecosystem.
- **San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA):** Promoting the responsible use of metrics and more holistic, qualitative evaluation of research.

Together, these frameworks provide a coherent foundation for embedding CoARA principles within existing institutional practice.

Our CoARA commitments include:

1. **Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research** in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.
2. **Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation** for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
3. **Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics**, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.
4. **Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations** in research assessment.

These core commitments are supported by six practical commitments - three commitments to enable the move towards new research assessment criteria, tools and processes, and three commitments to facilitate mutual learning, communicate progress and ensure that new approaches are evidence informed:

5. **Commit resources to reforming research assessment** as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.
6. **Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.**
7. **Raise awareness of research assessment reform** and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.
8. **Exchange practices and experiences** to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.
9. **Communicate progress** made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.
10. **Evaluate practices, criteria and tools** based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

As a member of CoARA, UWS agrees to communicate progress made and exchange good practice with other members of the Coalition. A key method for achieving this is through the creation of this action plan for reform, which all signatories and members of CoARA are required to produce.

These commitments apply across the institution to all processes and procedures where research assessment occurs. This includes:

- Internal preparations related to the assessment of UWS by assessment authorities and research funding organisations (e.g. the Research Excellence Framework, or other external submissions).
- Internal assessments of research projects, either before submission to an external funding body or as part of the allocation of internal research funding, or as part of making prize and award decisions.
- Internal assessments of individual staff members that are involved in research, for the purposes of allocating funding, recruitment and promotion, professional development review, and prize and award decisions.

It should be noted that processes such as recruitment, promotion and professional development review can include research assessment regardless of the contract type of the staff member. As part of our commitment to recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research, UWS commits to adopting a broad definition of its research community and considering all staff involved in the research endeavour when identifying in-scope research assessment processes.

Non-research-focused performance reviews of institutions, which may consider research alongside other factors, such as teaching, are outside the scope of CoARA. Nonetheless, it is recognised that research performance often plays a key role in performance reviews and benchmarking at an institutional level, and therefore the learning from our CoARA actions will be fed into these wider evaluation activities to avoid trickle-down effects on research and researcher assessment. For example, where the use of institutional rankings to benchmark is unavoidable due its relation to student recruitment, mitigations will be encouraged to reduce impact on researchers, research projects and research units, such as communicating the limitations of such measures and advising on appropriate communications.

Our Vision for Reform

Our vision is for UWS to be recognised as a leader in excellent, relevant and purposeful research that delivers meaningful impact in society, the economy and the environment, aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. UWS has seen significant growth in research and innovation activity in recent years, including increased external funding, expanding collaboration, and strengthened knowledge exchange and commercialisation. Building on this progress, Strategy 2030 sets a clear direction for continued growth in impactful, inclusive and globally connected research.

This ambition is supported by an established and evolving framework of research and innovation policies, procedures and guidance that promote high-quality, ethical and transparent research practices. These include, but are not limited to:

- The Code of Research Practice and Research Ethics, which underpins integrity and responsible conduct in research.
- The Research Data Management Procedure, supporting open, transparent and reproducible research.
- The Institutional Rights Retention Procedure, enabling open access and maximising the reach and impact of research outputs.
- Institutional authorship guidelines, promoting fairness and transparency in the recognition of contributions.
- A wider set of policies and initiatives supporting research culture, equality, diversity and inclusion, and researcher development.

Together, these frameworks reflect UWS's commitment to creating an environment in which high-quality research can thrive. However, the effectiveness of these policies depends fundamentally on how research is assessed and recognised in practice. Responsible research assessment is therefore a critical enabler of our strategic ambitions. It ensures that the behaviours and contributions we seek to promote—such as collaboration, openness, integrity, leadership, and impact—are meaningfully recognised and rewarded.

In order to achieve our ambitions, it is essential that our research community feels recognised for the full range of their contributions. Our research assessment practices must robustly and responsibly assess what they are intended to measure, encourage activity across the diversity of research outputs and roles that we value, and avoid creating incentives that undermine research quality, integrity, or inclusivity.

Over the period governed by this action plan, we will build on our existing strengths to establish a strong and coherent approach to responsible research assessment. This will ensure that our continued growth in research and innovation is underpinned by fair, transparent and values-driven evaluation practices. In order

to achieve these ambitions, research assessment at UWS must act as an enabler rather than a constraint, reinforcing the behaviours, contributions and values that underpin excellent and impactful research. This means ensuring that our research assessment practices and processes are fair, transparent and aligned with what we seek to achieve as a university, including recognising the diverse range of research and contributions across research, supporting inclusive career pathways, and encouraging high-quality, ethical and collaborative research practice.

This action plan establishes a strong foundation of responsible research assessment, which will strengthen consistency and coherence across our expanding research and innovation portfolio to build on the policy and cultural foundations already in place, aligning and connecting existing good practice to ensure that assessment practices fully support our strategic priorities. A key mechanism for delivering this will be the establishment of a collaborative group to bring together those responsible for the delivery of research assessment processes alongside colleagues leading on research-culture initiatives across the institution. This will support shared understanding, coordination and build capacity through the upskilling of key stakeholders in terms of their responsible research assessment literacy. In this way, responsible research assessment will be embedded into research culture initiatives and, simultaneously, reforms of research assessment will be aligned with broader institutional priorities.

To develop awareness and understanding beyond this group, responsible research assessment will be integrated into existing research development programmes wherever relevant. This applies to programmes for research active and research enabling staff as well as programmes for research leaders. Progress made against our action plan will be showcased internally and externally to enhance engagement, provide opportunity for feedback from staff, and demonstrate UWS's strength of commitment. We will also participate in sector-wide initiatives related to responsible research assessment, including membership of the UK CoARA National Chapter, to promote systemic change that benefits the whole higher education research ecosystem.

In recognition of UWS's size and growing research intensity, this initial plan adopts a focused approach to build institutional literacy and capacity, providing a strong foundation for future reforms. UWS's approach will be to use REF as a driver for good practice—ensuring that processes are robust, inclusive and aligned with our values, while avoiding unintended negative incentives. This will include targeted engagement with Unit of Assessment leads, training for decision-makers, and a structured post-REF evaluation to capture lessons learned and inform future development.

Our Action Plan (2026-2030)

Our first CoARA action plan has three core areas of focus: driving awareness and championing change; embedding alignment across institutional priorities; implementing focused reform activities. For each area, we have defined a clear overarching goal for 2030, supported by a set of broad, strategic actions to guide delivery and maintain flexibility in how these are achieved.

Recognising that both research and its assessment are continually evolving, and that responsible assessment must be sensitive to context, we have deliberately avoided developing a rigid, year-by-year action plan. Instead, progress against these overarching priorities will be monitored through annual reports to the Research Innovation Committee, with key activities for the coming year identified and agreed iteratively. This approach ensures responsiveness and the ability to adapt our actions in line with emerging needs and best practice.

Focus	Relevant Commitments	Goal	Actions
Driving Awareness and Championing Change	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9	Responsible research assessment will be widely understood, consistently communicated, and actively championed across the university, supported by visible leadership commitment, targeted engagement activities, and integration into institutional communications, training, and decision-making processes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embed responsible research assessment into development and training programmes to increase awareness amongst the research community. • Engage institutional leaders in responsible research assessment delivery to promote visible leadership and integrate principles into strategic discussions. • Communicate internally about commitments and progress. • Participate in sector initiatives to promote systemic change that benefits the whole higher education research ecosystem.
Embedding Alignment Across Institutional Priorities	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7	Responsible research assessment will be integrated into delivery of UWS's research strategy and related research culture initiatives, ensuring that policies, processes, and practices across areas such as open research, research integrity, equality, diversity and inclusion, and staff development collectively support an inclusive environment that enables high-quality research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convene key stakeholders involved in enhancing UWS's research cultures to enable mutually beneficial knowledge exchange which embeds responsible research assessment in wider activity and ensures that targeted reforms align with wider priorities.

Focus	Relevant Commitments	Goal	Actions
Implementing Focused Reform Activities	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 10	Responsible research assessment will underpin UWS's REF 2029 submission, ensuring that preparations are transparent, fair, robust, and inclusive recognition of diverse contributions. Following REF 2029, the University will undertake a structured evaluation of its approach to identify lessons learned and opportunities for further reform, using these insights to strengthen and extend responsible research assessment practices in preparation for the subsequent CoARA action plan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue to, and identify further opportunities to, ground REF 2029 preparations, submissions and communications in CoARA commitments and in line with the UWS REF 2029 Code of Practice. • Conduct a post-REF evaluation and lessons-learned process to understand efficacy of activity, alignment with commitments, and opportunities for further reform beyond REF activities.